

Some Furocoumarins

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Furocoumarins have been obtained by fusing either a furan ring to the benzene nucleus of coumarins¹ or an α -pyrone ring to coumarans².

In this communication are described some furocoumarins synthesised by condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetyloumarins with phenacyl bromides in presence of an excess of potassium carbonate. 5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin and 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin, have thus been condensed with a number of substituted phenacyl bromides to afford furocoumarins (I & II a, b, c d). The starting coumarins used in these reactions were prepared by condensing resacetophenone with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and nitrobenzene³ and of phosphorus oxychloride and benzene⁴ respectively.

Procedure.—Furocoumarins were prepared by refluxing on a waterbath *o*-hydroxy-acetyloumarin (0.01 mole), a phenacyl bromide (0.0) mole), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.05 mole) and dry acetone (30 ml), for 15-20 hr. The cooled product on treatment with water afforded a dark coloured solid which after washing with water and dilute alcohol gave light yellow crystals from dilute acetic acid; yields, about 56%.

Melting points and analytical data of 5', 6'-furocoumarins (I a, b, c and d) from 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin and of 6', 7'-furocoumarins (II a, b, c and d) from 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin by condensing with phenacyl and *p*-methyl-, *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromophenacyl bromides are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE I
5', 6'-Furocoumarins

Compound	X	M.P. C.	Found %		Required%	
			C	H	C	H
I a	H	187	75.55	4.91	75.47	4.40
I b	CH ₃	204	76.17	5.36	75.90	4.82
I c	Cl	239	67.89	4.14	68.10	3.69
I d	Br	245	60.78	3.67	60.45	3.27

1. Spath and Pailer, *Ber.* 1935 68, 940.

2. Horning and Reiser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1948, 70, 3619, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1514.

3. Shah, Shah and Sethna, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 231.

4. Ekhtas and Desai, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1960, 8A, 567.

TABLE 2

6',7'-Furocoumarins

Compound	X	M. P. C.	Found%		Required%	
			C	H	C	H
II a	H	182	75.84	4.79	75.47	4.40
II b	(H ₃)	241	76.23	5.27	75.90	4.82
II c	Cl	254	68.57	4.11	68.10	3.69
II d	Br	263	60.76	3.60	60.45	3.27

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